

Constructing victims and perpetrators: a textual analysis of media discourses on sexual violence

Farah Ali³⁸

Abstract

Sexual violence has become increasingly visible in the public eye, which has in turn prompted scholarly research across disciplines to critically examine how such cases are handled, ranging from the investigation processes to how the accused and accusing parties are impacted. Linguistic research in particular has made an important contribution to our understanding of the role of language in interpreting and evaluating sexual violence by focusing on the narrations of specific cases. Yet linguistic perspectives are somewhat sparse with regard to mass media discourse, which can play an influential role in shaping discussions on sexual violence. This study examines discourse on sexual violence found in online news reports in the U.S., and specifically focuses on contrasts between different discourse participants. Findings reveal that news reports employ various linguistic strategies that distance sexual violence from their perpetrators (faculty, in the cases examined in this study) and offer disparate attention to perpetrators and victims. Given the increasing visibility of public discourse on sexual aggression and the power that such discourse has in influencing audiences, analyzing the language used to construct victims and perpetrators is crucial to our understanding of the various ways that sexual violence perpetuates injustice.

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Keywords

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³⁸ DePauw University, ORCID: 0000-0003-1587-6403, farahali@depauw.edu

Introduction

In recent years, discussions about sexual violence have gained a stronger presence in public discourse. While research on this topic is extensive in various disciplines, scholarship that examines the discursive aspects of sexual violence is limited. Scholarship in communication studies has focused on sexual violence in the workplace, and how it may be perpetuated through communication dynamics within organizational structures (Keyton, 1996). For example, Keyton et al. (2001) point out that within a workplace, institutional culture may informally or unknowingly facilitate sexual harassment. From a linguistic perspective, however, much of this valuable scholarship is no longer current (Ehrlich, 1999, 2002; Ehrlich and King, 1992; Henley et al., 1995; Wood and Rennie 1994), and more recent scholarship comes after a significant gap, perhaps in the wake of #MeToo and other social movements that have drawn attention to sexual violence (Izes, 2021; Palomino-Manjón, 2022; Viehbeck, 2020; Wilinsky & McCabe, 2021).

This research makes an important contribution to our understanding of the role of language in interpreting and evaluating sexual violence by focusing on the narrations of specific cases. However, one area of sexual violence discourse that has received little attention over the years is that which pertains to sexual violence in academia, which oftentimes involves unknown, confidential investigations, or otherwise goes unreported altogether. In some rare instances, these cases are publicized by media attention. Given that public discourse can exert significant power in positioning both the participants and the readers of a text (Fairclough, 1989), analyzing the linguistic strategies used to discursively construct victims³⁹ and perpetrators is crucial to our understanding of how injustices may be perpetuated beyond the sexual aggressions themselves. Critical discourse analysis (Fairclough, 1989), which approaches discourse from the perspective that language is a social practice replete with power asymmetries, is an especially useful tool for analyzing the ways in which language can be manipulated to perpetuate structural inequities in academia, particularly those which emerge between perpetrators and victims of sexual violence. Using this framework and focusing on news articles that cover university cases of faculty-on-student sexual violence, this study examines how publicly reported allegations at these universities are presented in the media. Furthermore, media discourse have the potential to transform agentive acts of sexual aggression to passive, agentless constructs that downplay the magnitude of trauma experienced by the victims, thus upholding the “not that bad” mantra of rape culture (Gay, 2018). It is thus paramount to critically examine and reevaluate the production of such discourse, such that perpetrator accountability is pulled out from the periphery and becomes a focal point in discussions about sexual violence.

1. Multidisciplinary perspectives on sexual violence

Social movements like #MeToo and #TimesUp have prompted increasing numbers of sexual violence victims to come forward to share past aggressions that they have experienced, making these acts of violence more visible in the public eye. While many institutions and places of

³⁹ While *victim* and *survivor* are two frequently used terms in discussions about sexual violence, I choose to employ the term *victim* for the purposes of this article, as it is the more widely used term in criminal justice contexts. By comparison, *survivor* often implies that one has or is going through the recovery process (Sexual Assault Kit Initiative, 2015).

employment have taken actions to address sexual violence through awareness initiatives and the creation of Title IX offices, sexual violence remains a problem in both personal and professional spheres. Consequently, a great deal of research across disciplines has critically examined how such cases are handled. Scholarship in law and psychology are especially well-established (Shechory Bitton and Jaeger, 2019; Cahn, 2018; Fedina et. al, 2018; Ferrão and Gonçalves, 2015; Grubb and Turner, 2012; Holland, Cortina and Freyd, 2018; Lim, 2017; Philadelphoff-Puren, 2003; Shen, 2011), with works focusing on various aspects of sexual violence, including measuring the prevalence of such acts in the workplace, victim blaming ideologies, investigation processes, media reporting, and how the accused and accusing parties are impacted. In many of these contexts, the accusing parties who have been victimized often receive unfavorable treatment throughout the legal process. For instance, Cahn (2018) argues that cases of sexual violence frequently disempower women by employing the “reasonable woman standard,” which serves as a guideline for determining instances of sexual harassment, and bases such evaluations on what a “reasonable woman” would deem inappropriate. Cahn argues that this standard not only fails to hold perpetrators to any standards of behavior, but also fails to consider the many complexities of a client’s situation, such as the victim’s and perpetrator’s distinctive positionalities, as well as intersectional identities that may influence what behaviors may be deemed appropriate. Moreover, this standard oversimplifies and obscures definitions of sexual violence as that being a matter of gendered perspectives (i.e. a “reasonable woman” being regarded as more sensitive to harassment compared to other genders).

Victim-centric discourse and beliefs are certainly prevalent in matters of sexual violence. Ferrão and Gonçalves (2015) analyzed 46 empirical studies that examined observer variables in victim blaming, and found that most studies showed that men held the victim more responsible for her situation than women did. They also found that higher scores on sexist ideologies and accepting attitudes towards rape corresponded to a greater tendency toward victim blame, while higher rape empathy corresponded with decreased victim blame. Victim blaming, by definition, shifts the responsibility of sexual violence away from the perpetrator, thus failing to justly assign accountability. In order to counter this misattribution of blame, some have taken to publicly naming perpetrators. In 2017, for instance, lawyer Raya Sarkar published a list of 70 alleged academic sexual offenders on Facebook. While this generated heavy criticism on the grounds that such public shaming stripped the accused of their right to due process, Sarkar's publication highlighted the absence of effective frameworks for accountability in academia, and even served as a catalyst for the #MeToo movement in India (Chakraborty, 2019). In a similar vein, academic consultant Karen Kelsky (2018) published a crowdsourced spreadsheet in which over 2,000 cases of sexual violence were reported by individuals in less than a year’s time.

It is also crucial to acknowledge that those who have suffered from sexual aggressions experience multiple levels of trauma that go even beyond the acts of aggression themselves. The processes of reporting, seeking accountability, and treatment are similarly traumatizing, in that they force victims to repeatedly relive their experiences and interact with institutional structures that may inflict other forms of violence on victims. For instance, in a medical and forensic context, Mulla (2014) argues that even legal and medical attention “imposes a particular violence on victims of sexual assault. This violence is born not from the intentions of individual forensic nurses who consciously set out to alienate the victim-patient with whom they are working, but rather from the particular institutional, professional, and historical location of forensic sexual assault intervention” (2014: 217). Additionally, in environments where there are social hierarchies that influence individuals' professional trajectories, victims commonly experience retaliation when they stand up to their aggressors (Mathews, 2019).

While Title IX offices exist in American universities to prohibit sex-based discrimination and encourage students to report sexual violence, these offices still fail to protect victims and instead prioritize the university's interests, as noted in Lorenz et al.'s (2021) paper, “Title IX isn’t for you, it’s for the university”: Sexual violence survivors’ experiences of institutional betrayal in Title IX investigations. (Lorenz et al., 2021) Such institutional betrayal and the retaliatory actions that follow (e.g. creating a hostile environment) can further traumatize a victim; as such, Garrick & Buck (2020) highlight the need for a trauma-informed taxonomy to better classify the toxic management tactics that create a hostile work environment. More than that, outside these institutional contexts, victims are also faced with the challenge of rebuilding themselves, body and mind. As Shen (2011) points out, criminal and civil law both fail victims of sexual violence, in that they do not recognize this set of struggles or the emotional expense involved in recovery.

Because notions about sexual violence are often shaped by the very discourses on this topic, it is critical that this data also be analyzed from a linguistic perspective. Presently, there is little research dedicated to this topic (Ehrlich, 1999, 2002; Ehrlich and King, 1992; Henley et. al 1995; Izes, 2021; Wood and Rennie, 1994). Some of this existing research looks at discourse on sexual violence, such as linguistic strategies used to position the two principal participants - the accused and the accuser - in terms of responsibility and victimhood. Ehrlich’s (2002) study, for example, examines participant orientation to gender within conversation analysis and in the context of a court case. Here, Ehrlich notes that (non)agency is discursively represented, such that the accusing parties designate the accused as the agent in nonconsensual sexual aggressions by positioning him as the grammatical subject of intentional and willful acts, while the recipients of such acts are the complainants. In contrast, both the accused and the judge in this court case are noted to use linguistic constructions that obscure agency, such as the passive construction. Additionally, the judge further distances the accused from responsibility by attributing the reported acts of sexual aggression to hormones, rather than the accused. (Ehrlich, 2002:743) While these studies reflect discursive practices from well over two decades ago, courtroom discourse evidently remains problematic: in a study of the *Commonwealth v. William Henry Cosby Jr* (2017) trial and (2018) retrial (pre- and post-#MeToo), Izes (2021) demonstrates that the performative power of the complainant is limited by other actors in the courtroom, namely the defense attorney, who plays on victim stereotypes and questions the complainant’s credibility as the victim. Such evaluations of the victim hinge on the notion of an ideal victim, whom Christie (1986) describes as one who can receive a great deal of sympathy (such as a child), and is strong enough to come forward, yet weak enough to not be a threat to others’ interests. Additionally, they do not contribute to their own victimization by being in the wrong place at the wrong time (Ricciardelli et al., 2021). These attitudes towards victims may also be shaped by the criminal justice system at large. Mack & McCann (2018), for instance, argue that not only is sexual violence a deeply engrained component of American culture, but that the U.S. criminal justice system is a deeply flawed enabler of racialized and gendered violence itself, asking if we can “admit that our police, courtrooms, and prisons are broken while also calling for a renewed investment in using those very resources to hold sexual predators accountable for their crimes?” (2018: 330). Harris (2019) similarly argues that academia as an institution is similarly problematic, and that university interventions in cases of sexual violence (e.g. Title IX offices) often reinforce and exacerbate systems of violence.

Media discourse also plays an important role in shaping our understanding of sexual violence. Some of the linguistic strategies noted above are similarly observed in Henley et al. (1995), where the authors examine active and passive constructions in media discourse relating to sexual and non-sexual violence. The authors highlight the significance that syntactic

construction can have on an audience's comprehension, pointing out that, although individuals typically encode overall meaning from discourse, syntax can still influence what information from an utterance is retained in one's memory; for instance, the use of the passive voice (e.g. passive: "the woman was raped"; active: "the man raped the woman") can lead a listener/reader to interpret the object of the sentence as being the most important element, rather than the agent, which may be deemphasized or omitted altogether. Word choice is similarly impactful: in a study of media representations of high profile sexual violence cases in American newspapers, Aroustamian (2020) found that euphemisms were widely used, particularly the word 'misconduct,' a term that is also used widely in institutional policies about sexual violence, which in turn understates the seriousness of these acts and the traumatic impacts they leave on victims. Discursive variation in media reports can also depend on the victims in question: Clark (1992) found that male perpetrators were more likely to be identified as "fiendish" (or with equally strong language) if the victims were considered sexually "unavailable" (e.g. wives), while more mild language was used to describe male perpetrators who preyed on women who were considered "available" or "unrespectable" (1992: 223). Various studies also demonstrate how discourses on sexual violence as reported in the media can transform one's interpretation of events: Acquaviva et al. (2021) examine student perceptions of sexual violence in the media through interviews with students and alumni, and found that most participants relied on media-based platforms as a source of information, which the authors further argued to be problematic due to the prominence of content that supports rape culture. They further note that this creates a cyclical issue, wherein misperceptions about sexual violence in the media and its subsequent consumption together perpetuate a culture that is hostile towards victims of sexual violence and overlooks perpetrators. This is further corroborated in a more recent study, in which Schanz & Jones (2023) found that media-watching habits were especially impactful on individuals' perceptions of the victim (rather than the perpetrator), such that the more one engaged in media, the more likely they were to blame the victim. Similarly, using the example of a widely publicized American rape trial from 2004, *Maouloud Baby v. the State of Maryland*, Ehrlich (2012) points out that discourse about this incident moved across different contexts - from the legal system to mainstream media - to the point that the discourse's meaning was recontextualized and transformed to reproduce patterns of gender inequality; for example, the coercion suffered by the victim in this case being reinterpreted as actual consent.

The (re)construction of consent in fact plays a significant role in shaping discourse on sexual violence, and can create ambiguities surrounding blame attribution (Ehrlich, 1998). Ehrlich points out that a "deficiency model" of miscommunication may be employed in sexual violence discourse in order to reevaluate the presence of consent. For example, in her study of a university sexual assault trial, Ehrlich indicates that both the defendant and the tribunal members who evaluated the guilt or innocence of the defendant employ this model to argue that neither the accused nor accusing party communicated their intentions effectively, which resulted in misinterpretations about the sexual acts in question. The complainants in this case were thus "deficient" in their attempts to effectively communicate non-consent. Kitzinger and Frith (1999) are similarly critical of expectations that often surround consent and refusal, and argue that the simplistic prescription of "just say no" can invalidate other equally valid strategies of refusal, such as silence or indirect verbal refusal. Kulbaga & Spencer (2019) also examine how even campus alerts issued by the police when incidents of sexual violence are reported fall short and can further perpetuate rape culture and obfuscate the notion of consent. In this vein, they suggest that descriptions of reported crimes and subsequent crime prevention tips should shift away from focusing on victim's behavior and/or a potential victim's behavior, respectively; instead, they should center the perpetrator's actions with the active voice, and

provide tips aimed at the community at large, as well as define consent according to feminist principles.

Discourse relating to blame attribution is also prevalent in social media: Stubbs-Richardson et al. (2018) examined discourse on Twitter about the Torrington and Steubenville Rape Trials and the Rehtaeh Parson's story of rape, victimization, and suicide, and found that - while many tweets attempted to debunk rape myths - many of the tweets on these stories strongly perpetuated rape culture through the construction of a virgin-whore binary among victims or downplaying the significance of these cases. Particularly noteworthy was their finding that Twitter users who engaged in victim blaming were more likely to be retweeted and have more followers than Twitter users who showed support for victims. Similarly, in a study of the comments sections in online periodicals (including Facebook), Zaleski et al. (2016) found that nearly every article analyzed had corresponding comments that supported the perpetrator in question, and over 25% of the comments overall included victim blaming statements. These findings show important role that social media has in constructing and perpetuating rape culture through victim-centric discourse and misattributed blame.

While such research makes an important contribution to our understanding of the role of language in interpreting and evaluating sexual violence, there is a dearth of up-to-date studies, which in turn understates the importance that language has in discussions about sexual violence. Additionally, it is especially crucial to address sexual violence discourse in university settings, in part because sexual violence is rampant in academia (Shrier 1996), as evident from Raya Sarkar's and Karen Kelsky's public lists of cases, but also because - as Kulbaga & Spencer (2019) note - many universities function as “campuses of nonconsent” that “replicate the power dynamics and structural oppression of the culture at large, which often fails to respect, value, and validate the experiences of women, queer and trans students, students of color, immigrants and refugees, and other oppressed and marginalized populations” (2019: 5). Furthermore, it is a clear abuse of power in the many instances where the perpetrator is a faculty member and the victim is a student, allowing the former unmitigated control over the latter's academic and professional trajectory. Moreover, in highlighting sexual violence as it is addressed on university campuses is especially crucial in scholarly research; because many of us are in faculty roles and may act as the confidantes for student victims and thus serving as first responders in such situations, we have a professional responsibility to actively participate in institutional responses to sexual violence (Sharoni and Klocke, 2019).

As evidenced by much of the research cited above, public discourse intended for mass audiences can become the site for discussions on sexual violence. Such discourse resembles that of a monologue, where the audience is a passive participant that does not contribute directly to the discourse (Fairclough, 1995). Not only that, but such discourse is often manufactured by authors who go unnamed (e.g. institutional policies) or are otherwise not prominently featured (e.g. news articles). This means that the active participants of such one-sided discourse can wield significant power in shaping individual ideologies and beliefs. Fairclough (1989) describes the power of the media: “The hidden power of discourse and capacity of the capitalist class and other power- holders to exercise this power depend on systematic tendencies in news reporting and other media activities. A single text on its own is quite insignificant: the effects of media power are cumulative, working through the repetition of particular ways of handling causality and agency, particular ways of positioning the reader, and so forth.” (1989: 54) This is particularly noteworthy in the study of discourse on sexual aggressions, where gendered inequality is often constructed and reproduced vis-a-vis discourse on blame attribution, a notion that is strongly intertwined with the concept of agency. As previous research has shown, the conceptualization and assignment of agency in sexual violence discourse plays a key role in

how accountability may or may not be attached to victims and perpetrators. Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA) is thus an efficacious tool for analyzing publicly disseminated discourse on sexual violence, as this approach allows us to examine language use through a sociopolitical lens, whereby discourse can be shown to play a significant role in enacting, reproducing and/or contesting unequal power dynamics among discourse participants. (Van Dijk, 2015). Fairclough's (1995) framework for CDA is particularly relevant for the present study, where discourse is analyzed from various angles: (1) linguistic analyses of texts (e.g. syntactic analysis of texts); (2) analysis of the production and consumption of discourse; (3) analysis of discourse as a reflection of socio-cultural practices and structures.

2. Analytical framework and methods

This study examines how publicly reported allegations of sexual violence at universities are presented in the media. Focusing on allegations involving student complainants and faculty respondents, this study is guided by the following research questions:

1. What linguistic features and/or strategies does media discourse employ to describe cases of sexual violence that have occurred at the above universities?
2. How are faculty perpetrators and student victims represented?

In addressing these questions, we can gain a better understanding of the language of sexual violence, and more importantly, open discussions on how universities can more effectively address sexual violence in any type of public discourse. This is a necessary step towards informing best practices in how universities outline their own procedures for investigating sexual violence, providing accountability, and ensuring more just resolutions to student victims. The present study relies on texts taken from online news sources that report cases of faculty sexual violence against students. In each case, the faculty members in question have received accusations of sexual violence, ranging from verbal harassment to rape. After searching through Google using a variety of search terms (including “university”, “sexual violence”, “sexual misconduct”, “rape”, “sexual assault”), I chose cases based on the availability of multiple news articles about them, while also making an effort to focus on cases that represent both public and private universities across the U.S. For each case of sexual violence, I collected three news articles, since in many cases this was the maximum number of articles available in a given moment: two articles from local or national news (depending on availability), and one from the online news sources produced by the universities in question, when available. Using ten different cases from 2017-2023, a total of thirty news articles are analyzed and center around sexual violence cases at the following ten universities:

1. Boston University
2. Harvard University
3. Johns Hopkins University
4. Ohio University
5. New Mexico State University
6. Stanford University
7. The Juilliard School
8. University of Michigan
9. University of South Carolina
10. University of Virginia

Additionally, this period was selected for the purpose of examining (a) recent discourse, and (b) discourse produced in the wake of #MeToo, which gained intense momentum across social media platforms in 2017. While I sought out articles based on the availability of reports from multiple news outlets, in each instance, the respondents were all male faculty members while the complainants were all female students, a distribution that reflects statistics on sexual violence: in the U.S., an estimated 82% of all juvenile victims and 90% of adult victims of sexual violence are female (Rape, Abuse and Incest National Network, 2021). While not within the scope of the present study, I also collected texts that discuss policies and procedures relating to sexual violence that are publicly available on university websites; specifically, the universities where the reported sexual violence cases took place, and so the present data set forms part of a larger corpus consisting of discourse on sexual violence. Finally, it is also worth noting that “sexual misconduct” is the operative term used to describe nonconsensual acts of a sexual nature in some of the texts; however, I choose to employ the term “sexual violence” and argue that this is a more accurate term to describe such acts, while “misconduct” - a term also used to describe comparatively mild infractions such as plagiarism - erases the aggression and resulting trauma that is experienced by victims.

Using NVivo 12 (2018) to code data, all texts were analyzed through a framework of Critical Discourse Analysis (Fairclough, 1989). I first completed initial readings in order to identify key themes in the texts. Here, I used NVivo to organize different themes into individual ‘nodes,’ and times aggregated these individual ‘child nodes’ under a ‘parent node’ when I was able to connect groups of specific themes to broader ones. Among these themes, those that related to vocabulary and grammatical constructions (e.g., the use of the active vs. passive voice, terminology used to describe events and actors) were categorized as descriptive components of the text. The analysis also consists of interpretive components, such as an examination of the participants involved in these discourses, including the producers of the texts, the people to whom they are referring, the readers, and essentially how various participants’ identities are discursively constructed, such as the complainant and the respondent, and how blame is either assigned to or shifted away from the accused, and how participants may be discursively constructed as either “victim” or “perpetrator”.

3. Results

Using the methodology described above, various themes stood out as ones that underscore the often problematic ways in which sexual violence is construed in media discourse. In this section I look at participant positionality, and focus specifically on how (faculty) respondents are portrayed.

The first point of analysis includes an examination of word choice used to describe sexual violence, specifically in news headlines. Next, I examine how active and passive verbal constructions (do not) assign agency to complainants and/or respondents. Next, the analysis centers on respondent background information being foregrounded in news articles. Finally, I explore the theme of retaliation as it relates to complainants’ reported experiences.

3.1. Conceptualizing sexual violence

Headlines - written either by the article author or an editor - serve a purpose distinct from the news articles that they advertised: not only do they offer a succinct summary of the article content, they are also meant to grab the attention of the reader. In this section, I focus on how these snippets of discourse conceptualize sexual violence through word choice.

As previously noted, “sexual misconduct” is often the term used to describe sexual violence in university policy discourse, and so in some cases, this terminology is mirrored in news articles, as is in the following instance at the Juilliard School, involving a professor making sexual advances and entering into sexual relationships with students:

Juilliard Fires Professor After Sexual Misconduct Inquiry

(*New York Times*. Case: The Juilliard School).

Juilliard fires former chair after sexual misconduct investigation

(*NPR*. Case: The Juilliard School)

While the use of such terminology may reflect an intention to remain consistent with the language used by the university and therefore ensure more accurate reporting, this consistency is not always present across different news sources, as is in the case of reports relating to incidents at Johns Hopkins University, where a variety of terms are used:

Two Professors Leave Johns Hopkins over Misconduct

(*The Scientist*. Case: Johns Hopkins University)

Here’s what happened when Maryland students forced colleges to confront sexual assault

(*The Baltimore Sun*. Case: Johns Hopkins University)

Students protest the University’s mishandling of sexual violence cases

(*JHU Newsletter*. Case: Johns Hopkins University)

In these examples, terminology ranges greatly, including a headline that simply refers to professors’ actions as “misconduct,” removing the sexual nature of these acts entirely from the headline. Not only that, in this headline, the two professors and the act of misconduct are disconnected from one another, as the headline does not explicitly assign the misconduct as “theirs,” which renders these acts as agentless ones.

On the other end of the spectrum, and indeed in a rare instance, “sexual violence” is used to describe the offenses in the university publication, *JH Newsletter*. It is also worth noting that this a student-run publication featuring student authors, and that the article centers on student protests surrounding the mishandling of such cases; as such, it might be expected that in this context, the use of “misconduct” might be challenged through naming these acts as violence.

3.2. Passive and active constructions

Shifting the analysis to media discourse, one of the most salient linguistic strategies employed across different news pieces is the distribution of passive and active constructions and the ways in which each grammatical form is assigned to the involved parties. While active constructions focus on the actor performing the action, the passive construction focuses on the action itself.

These forms can be contrasted with the following examples: “She read the book” (active); “The book was read (by her)” (passive).

As this example denotes, the latter construction allows for the actor to be removed altogether, which can play a critical role in how individuals interpret discourse relating blame and responsibility. In the present study, news articles used passive constructions more frequently to describe the respondents’ actions in comparison to those of the complainants:

The review panel supported the investigator’s finding that “kissing and some degree of touching” occurred in Casey’s car at the restaurant, and that Casey’s behavior was unwanted and unwelcome.

(*Daily Progress News*. Case: University of Virginia)

...she was harassed by Kalyango.

(*The Athens News*. Case: Ohio University)

He was found to have engaged in “sexual harassment of a student, abusive and bullying behavior toward trainees, and other inappropriate behaviors...”

(*The Scientist*. Case: John Hopkins University)

In these brief excerpts, the descriptions of the accused parties’ actions employ constructions that center on the actions themselves, rather than the individuals involved. While each description does mention an actor (either by name or pronoun) and the first example simply reiterates university discourse by directly quoting a university investigator, the sexual aggressions are the focus in all of these descriptions: “kissing and some degree of touching occurred”; “she was harassed”; and, in a more complex, yet ultimately passive construction: “he was found to have engaged in sexual harassment of a student”.

These constructions shift the actor into a less conspicuous and distanced position from the acts in question, which can leave a reader to interpret the actor’s role as unimportant. Moreover, these constructions also employ nominalization (i.e. “kissing” as a noun instead of “he kissed” as a subject and verb), which further emphasize actions rather than the agents responsible for them. While news reports also employ active, verbal constructions to describe respondents’ actions, these instances typically occur in the form of direct or indirect quotes from the complainants, thereby placing them in an active role alongside the respondents:

Kimberly S. Latta wrote on Facebook on Sunday that Mr. Moretti had raped her in the mid-1980s when he was a visiting professor at the University of California at Berkeley.

(*The Chronicle*. Case: Stanford University)

Dr. Lisa Schievelbein, a former University student who graduated in 2001, filed a Title IX claim against English Prof. John Casey in November 2017 with allegations that he sexually assaulted her while she was a student.

(*The Cavalier*. Case: University of Virginia)

In these examples, the respondents are clearly assigned a more active role with respect to the actions that they are accused of, which could be interpreted in different ways. Assigning them an active role may be a means of empowering the complainants; or, since both statements are premised as being second-hand reports made by the complainants, they may emphasize the speculative nature of such claims.

In other instances, complainants are assigned a more agentive role in relation to the respondents' actions, but at times in a more implicit manner:

Sexual Harassment Allegations Wipe a Name Off the Map: Accusations of sexual harassment have ended the careers of men in many fields, forcing them out of prominent posts and ending relationships with shame. Now the impact has rippled all the way to Antarctic glaciers.

(New York Times. Case: Boston University)

Sexual Harassment Claims Made Against Prominent Boston University Scientist

(WBUR News. Case: Boston University)

In these extracts from different news sources that reference the same case, there is no mention of the complainant. However, the actors in each one are the sexual harassment allegations/claims, while the respondent - a Boston University scientist - is the recipient of the actor's actions; namely, having his name wiped "off the map".

The first example goes one step further and connects this specific case at Boston University to a broader pattern in which sexual harassment allegations play an active role in affecting the lives of men, who are removed from any agentive role while allegations have ended the careers, forced them out of prominent posts, and ended relationships. While no individual is explicitly attached to the allegations, a possible extrapolation would be that complainants are responsible for allegations, and thus responsible for the consequences that respondents experience.

In these examples, then, the complainants are constructed as perpetrators, the respondents as victims, and the central actions connecting them - sexual harassment - become speculative rather than factual knowledge.

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3.3. Foregrounding background information

Another pattern noted in news reports was the inclusion of peripheral or irrelevant information relating to participants involved in cases of sexual violence. The vast majority of these instances, however, focused on background information relating to faculty respondents and typically consisted of laudatory descriptions of these respondents' achievements:

The retired professor is Franco Moretti, a noted expert on digital humanities and a literary critic. The other professor, who died in 2007, is Jay Fliegelman, an influential scholar of American literature and cultural studies.

(The Chronicle. Case: Stanford University)

Despite his two-year leave from Stanford, Chu noted, Fliegelman remained a prominent scholar up to his death at the age of 58.

(Stanford University News. Case: Stanford University)

He was then an assistant professor in earth sciences at BU, widely recognized already for outstanding research on the East Antarctic Ice Sheet. His research changed the way people understand the stability of that ice sheet. He has a glacier named after him.

(*WBUR News*. Case: Boston University)

Casey has taught at UVa's creative writing program since joining the faculty in 1972 and won the National Book Award in 1989 for his novel "Spartina".

(*Daily Progress News*. Case: University of Virginia)

As shown in the above examples, news reports highlight respondents' academic achievements and prominence in their respective fields. While such descriptions constitute background information, their lack of relevance to the specific cases of sexual violence in question thus distracts from the core information (namely, the acts of aggression that these respondents are accused of committing), bringing into question what function the inclusion of such information serves.

Given that they have been placed in the foreground, these laudatory comments may serve to offset the negativity associated with their reported behavior. This effectively gives as much weight (or more) to their professional accomplishments as their alleged offenses, rendering the impact of academic achievement as equally or more significant than the impact of sexual violence.

By comparison, there is virtually no background information presented about complainants other than neutral comments indicating where complainants worked, such as in the below example:

Ms. Latta, who was a graduate student in English there at the time, went on to teach English at the University of Pittsburgh and Saint Louis University before switching careers. Today she is a psychotherapist and yoga instructor.

(*The Chronicle*. Case: Stanford University)

Juxtaposing Latta's expertise in "English" against the more specific areas such as "digital humanities" (Moretti) and "American literature and cultural studies" (Fliegelman), complainants' professional profiles are represented as inconsequential in comparison to respondents. This is further reinforced by the lack of authority given to Latta in relation to her work, having been described as studying and teaching it, while Moretti is "an expert" and Fliegelman "an influential scholar." While all such details are irrelevant to reports of sexual violence, these unbalanced descriptions suggest that victims matters less if they are reportedly less influential than their abusers, thus trivializing the gravity of sexual violence as a function of one's scholarly prominence.

3.4. Retaliation

Much like in the case of university policies, retaliation was a recurring theme in news media as well. While university policies explicitly label retaliation as prohibited and punishable conduct, a number of complainants were still reported to have feared retaliation, indicating that this was

one of the primary reasons that they did not report their professors' inappropriate behavior during their time as students:

Boyle, who admitted to lying in 2012 about the validity of sexual misconduct allegations against Kalyango because she had several important career opportunities that wouldn't have happened without her work under programs directed by the professor, came forward after being contacted by a journalism faculty member, according to the report.

(The Athens News. Case: Ohio University)

When she got back to Boston University from Antarctica, Willenbring says she did not report the abuse she says she suffered. She says she feared retaliation. That, she says, prompted her to wait all these years until she received tenure.

(WBUR News. Case: Boston University)

As illustrated in these examples and in the previous section, institutional prohibition of retaliation is often not sufficient to allay the concerns of victims, as retaliation can take many forms and can manifest within the university environment (e.g. course grades and degree conferral), but also outside one's university, in the form of job opportunities and promotions. In many instances, such as in the cases noted above, victims may wait until they are out of the reach of the offending party and the degree-granting institution, and in a more stable professional situation before reporting the abuse they have experienced, which in many instances may take years, such as in the case of Willenbring, who waited until she was not only employed at another university, but also after she had received tenure. This also means that the fear of retaliation can last long after an individual has graduated and left an abusive environment.

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Discussion and conclusion

This study examined how publicized sexual violence allegations at universities are presented in the media. This study has shown that news media can indeed discursively construct both "victims" and "perpetrators" by way of (re)assigning or omitting agency when describing acts, such that discourse relating to victims fails to recognize the lack of free will they may have been able to exercise in the moments of aggression. This is evident in the use of the passive voice when describing the actions of perpetrators, seen both in this study and that of Henley et al. (1995). Thus, such discourse creates a false sense of equal footing between complainants and respondents, where the female student victims are presumed to hold the same degree of agency as the male faculty perpetrators and therefore responsible for the aggressions committed against them, as noted in Ferrão and Gonçalves (2015). News media may further manipulate participants' identities by foregrounding fairly irrelevant background information. When such information is presented with commendatory language, this can shape how readers interpret the broader message of the new story (specifically, the succession of events involved in a sexual violence case), as well as how we assign responsibility for sexual violence. This is further evidenced even in the word choice used to describe sexual violence, particularly in news headlines, where "misconduct" is often used - if inconsistently - to describe these acts. As such, findings from this study support those from previous studies (Acquaviva et al., 2021; Schanz & Jones, 2023) that highlight the problematic representations of sexual violence in the media.

Retaliation is also a key theme that appears in media discourse. As some of the news articles highlighted, victims often fear retaliation as a negative repercussion, as is also reflected in previous studies (Lorenz et al., 2021; Mathews, 2019), which have critiqued the limited and at times detrimental effect of institutional involvement in sexual violence cases (i.e. Title IX offices). Moreover, victims may fear retaliation for a significant amount of time, even after they graduate, oftentimes because they are still in professionally precarious positions. While this long-lasting fear can be in part the result of trauma, ongoing distress over the possibility of retaliation can also be telling of the systemic nature of abuse in academia. If an otherwise meritorious individual can fear punishment or having accolades withheld even outside their degree-granting institutions, we must ask ourselves to what extent (rather than “if”) abuse is the currency of academia and how university communities can better address the issue of sexual violence in order to maximize prevention, ensure accountability, and provide support to those who have been abused.

While this study serves to call attention to a significant issue in academia, the data I analyzed represents a small fraction of reported cases, to say nothing of the investigations that remain confidential, as well as cases of sexual violence that go unreported. Furthermore, a larger dataset would have allowed for examining the role of participant identities in shaping media discourse. For instance, specific respondents that were references in news articles included a mix of faculty who were white and people of color. While I observed that irrelevant, laudatory comments were made only about white faculty and excluded respondents of color, much more extensive data collection is required to determine whether or not this is a pattern in news media. Additionally, other modalities may also provide additional insight into how news media construct different participants involved in cases of sexual violence. While my initial analyses included an examination of photos found in news articles and I noted that there was a relatively even distribution of photos of respondents and complainants, further investigation with a larger collection of news articles is required for more conclusive observations.

Additionally, a diachronic analysis of data (specifically, news reports pre- and post-#MeToo) would provide insight on whether or not discourse is moving towards more equitable treatment of participants involved in sexual violence. Finally, further analysis of university policies that examine how terminology relating to sexual violence is operationalized may also be telling of what forms of sexual violence are legitimized or overlooked in an academic context, since more overt acts of aggression are typically highlighted, while subtler aggressions may not be accounted for.

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Appendix

News Articles

Boston University

Sexual Harassment Claims Made Against Prominent Boston University Scientist
<https://www.wbur.org/edify/2017/10/27/marchant-antartica-allegations> (Accessed 3.01.2024)

BU professor fired for harassment charges
<https://dailyfreepress.com/blog/2019/04/19/bu-professor-fired-for-harassment-charges-2/> (Accessed 3.01.2024)

Sexual Harassment Allegations Wipe a Name Off the Map
<https://www.nytimes.com/2018/09/24/us/glacier-david-marchant-sexual-harassment.html> (Accessed 3.01.2024)

Harvard University

Harvard professor to retire as he faces multiple allegations of sexual harassment

<https://www.washingtonpost.com/news/grade-point/wp/2018/03/06/harvard-professor-to-retire-as-he-faces-multiple-allegations-of-sexual-harassment/> (Accessed 3.01.2024)

Harvard bans ex-professor after finding 'unwelcome sexual conduct' spanned four decades

<https://www.usatoday.com/story/news/nation/2019/05/09/harvard-university-professor-jorge-dominguez-sexual-harassment-misconduct-metoo-title-ix/1154497001/> (Accessed 3.01.2024)

Harvard Prof. Dominguez Stripped of Emeritus Status Following Conclusion of Title IX Investigation

<https://www.thecrimson.com/article/2019/5/9/dominguez-investigation-closes/> (Accessed 3.01.2024)

Johns Hopkins University

Here's what happened when Maryland students forced colleges to confront sexual assault

https://www.baltimoresun.com/education/bs-md-colleges-sexual-harass-20190827-u5ixpqqg3ujhpnbo2rj3sebnzyi-story.html?fbclid=IwAR0aoX84XLhf-PDJjQLcweXi-4erVHnU0NdNGiZ8wOdubqMyG2_pLw5R9bI (Accessed 3.01.2024)

Two Professors Leave Johns Hopkins over Misconduct

<https://www.the-scientist.com/news-opinion/two-professors-leave-johns-hopkins-over-misconduct-66196> (Accessed 3.01.2024)

Students protest the University's mishandling of sexual violence cases

<https://www.jhunewsletter.com/article/2018/12/students-protest-the-universitys-mishandling-of-sexual-violence-cases> (Accessed 3.01.2024)

New Mexico State University

Former professors accused in New Mexico State University's sexual harassment lawsuit

<https://kfoxtv.com/news/instagram/former-professors-accused-in-new-mexico-state-universitys-sexual-harassment-lawsuit> (Accessed 3.01.2024)

Woman sues NMSU, former professor for sexual harassment

<https://www.krqe.com/news/new-mexico/woman-sues-nmsu-former-professor-for-sexual-harassment/> (Accessed 3.01.2024)

Lawsuit alleges decade of sexual misconduct by former New Mexico State University professor

<https://kvia.com/news/new-mexico/2024/01/16/lawsuit-alleges-decade-of-sexual-misconduct-by-former-new-mexico-state-university-professor/> (Accessed 3.01.2024)

Ohio University

Ohio University professor found by Title IX office to have sexually harassed two women shouldn't lose tenure, Faculty Senate says

https://www.athensnews.com/news/campus/ohio-university-professor-found-by-title-ix-office-to-have-sexually-harassed-two-women-shouldn/article_90924985-cbf6-5ddf-b0f5-198f851ca19d.html (Accessed 3.01.2024)

Faculty Senate Committee recommends Kalyango be reinstated following sexual harassment investigation

https://www.athensmessenger.com/news/faculty-senate-committee-recommends-kalyango-be-reinstated-following-sexual-harassment-investigation/article_0252a61a-f734-5076-bda9-a29858b7fbdc.html (Accessed 3.01.2024)

Student Senate: Students speak about sexual assault following Kalyango recommendation

<https://www.thepostathens.com/article/2021/02/student-senate-sexual-assault-yusuf-kalyango-ohio-university> (Accessed 3.01.2024)

Stanford University

2 Women Say Stanford Professors Raped Them Years Ago <https://www.chronicle.com/article/2-Women-Say-Stanford/241749> (Accessed 3.01.2024)

Two women accuse former Stanford professors of sexual assault
<https://www.stanforddaily.com/2017/11/09/two-women-accuse-former-stanford-professors-of-sexual-assault/>
(Accessed 3.01.2024)

In university sexual harassment cases, a chilling power dynamic
<https://www.eastbaytimes.com/2017/12/07/in-university-sexual-harassment-cases-a-chilling-power-dynamic/>
(Accessed 3.01.2024)

University of Michigan

U-M professor to resign following multiple sexual assault allegations
<https://nbc25news.com/features/school/u-m-professor-to-resign-following-multiple-sexual-assault-allegations>
(Accessed 3.01.2024)

Time's Up For University Of Michigan Professor Who Made At Least 26 Female Students Uncomfortable
https://www.deadlinedetroit.com/articles/28135/time_s_up_for_university_of_michigan_professor_who_made_at_least_26_female_students_uncomfortable (Accessed 3.01.2024)

Daily investigation finds divergence in U-M, outside organization's handling of allegations against CSE professor
<https://www.michigandaily.com/news/daily-investigation-finds-divergence-in-u-m-outside-organizations-handling-of-allegations-against-cse-professor/> (Accessed 3.01.2024)

University of South Carolina

Former USC student sues, alleges professor exploited her PTSD to sexually harass her
<https://www.thestate.com/news/local/education/article250166905.html> (Accessed 3.01.2024)

How USC is stumbling in handling sexual harassment and assault cases like other colleges
https://www.postandcourier.com/columbia/news/how-usc-is-stumbling-in-handling-sexual-harassment-and-assault-cases-like-other-colleges/article_4c4022de-9ebe-11eb-9140-ab4a198b9631.html (Accessed 3.01.2024)

History professor accused of sexual assault removed from campus, will remain on USC payroll
<https://www.dailygamecock.com/article/2021/03/history-professor-accused-of-sexual-assault-has-been-removed-from-campus-remains-on-uscs-payroll-poag-news> (Accessed 3.01.2024)

University of Virginia

UVa Panel Finds Casey Responsible of Inappropriate Sexual Contact with a Student
https://www.dailyprogress.com/news/uva/uva-panel-finds-casey-responsible-of-inappropriate-sexual-contact-with/article_39bf3996-ff3e-11e8-8786-57a7d7c74cca.html (Accessed 3.01.2024)

UVa panel recommends ban for professor after sexual harassment findings
https://www.roanoke.com/news/virginia/uva-panel-recommends-ban-for-professor-after-sexual-harassment-findings/article_f6fda89c-c546-5ea5-b0a4-d4a3dfd423b9.html (Accessed 3.01.2024)

Former student accuses U.Va. Professor John Casey of sexual assault
<https://www.cavalierdaily.com/article/2018/05/former-student-accuses-john-casey-of-sexual-assault> (Accessed 3.01.2024)

The Juilliard School

Juilliard Fires Professor After Sexual Misconduct Inquiry

<https://www.nytimes.com/2023/06/08/arts/music/juilliard-fires-professor-accused-of-sexually-harassing-students.html> (Accessed 3.01.2024)

Juilliard fires professor after independent investigation finds credible evidence of misconduct
<https://www.cnn.com/2023/06/10/us/new-york-juilliard-professor-fired-misconduct-case/index.html> (Accessed 3.01.2024)

Juilliard fires former chair after sexual misconduct investigation
<https://www.npr.org/2023/06/08/1181179315/juilliard-fires-former-chair-after-sexual-misconduct-investigation>
(Accessed 3.01.2024)